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Master Thesis

Estimation of the geothermal potential in the Loranca sub-basin, NE Alto Guadiana area (Central Spain) based on 3D modelling and petrophysical properties

Author: Johan Andrés Tibavija Guio

Tutors: Dra. Concepción Ayala (GEO3BCN-CSIC)
Dr. Enrique Gómez Rivas (UB)
Dra. Ivone Jiménez Munt (GEO3BCN-CSIC)

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a methodology for estimating the geothermal potential of the Loranca sub-basin, located in the north-eastern part of the Alto Guadiana region (Central Spain). The approach integrates rock petrophysical data with a 3D geological modelling. Laboratory analyses of rock samples collected near the study area were conducted to characterise key petrophysical properties, including thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, specific heat capacity, and density. These petrophysical parameters, combined with the regional boundary conditions, were incorporated into a 3D geological model of the area using Geomodeller software to simulate temperature distribution with depth. The geological and thermal models were exported and processed with the 3DHIP_Calculator software to evaluate deep geothermal potential. 3DHIP_Calculator code, through a probabilistic Monte Carlo approach, provided estimates of the Heat in Place (HIP) and Recoverable Heat (Hrec) for the aquifer. These models illustrate depth-temperature relationships and highlight the Jurassic aquifer as the most promising lithology for heat storage. The results reveal a low geothermal potential for the Jurassic unit, suitable mainly for low-enthalpy geothermal applications (heating and cooling systems, balneotherapy, greenhouses, etc.). This methodology reduces uncertainty in resource estimation and provides a reproducible tool for future geothermal assessments.

KEYWORDS: Geothermal, Petrophysics, 3D Thermal Modeling, Heat in Place, Recoverable Heat.

RESUM

Aquest estudi presenta una metodologia per estimar el potencial geotèrmic de la subconques de Loranca, situada a la part nord-oriental de la regió de l'Alt Guadiana (Espanya Central). L'aproximació integra dades petrofísiques de roca amb un modelatge geològic en 3D. Es van dur a terme anàlisis de laboratori de mostres de roca recollides prop de l'àrea d'estudi per caracteritzar les propietats petrofísiques clau, incloent la conductivitat tèrmica, la difusivitat tèrmica, la capacitat tèrmica específica i la densitat. Aquests paràmetres petrofísics, combinats amb condicions de contorn regional, es van incorporar a un model geològic en 3D de la zona utilitzant el programari Geomodeller per simular la distribució de temperatura amb profunditat. Els models geològics i tèrmics van ser exportats i processats amb el programari 3DHIP per avaluar el potencial geotèrmic profund. El codi 3DHIP, a través d'un enfocament probabilístic de Monte Carlo, proporciona estimacions de Calor en Lloc (HIP) i Calor Recuperable (Hrec) per a l'aqüífer. Aquests models il·lustren les relacions de temperatura de profunditat i destaquen l'aqüífer Juràssic com la litologia més prometedora per a l'emmagatzematge de calor. Els resultats revelen un baix potencial geotèrmic per a la unitat Juràssica, adequat principalment per a aplicacions geotèrmiques de baixa entalpia (calefacció i refrigeració, balneoteràpia, hivernacles, etc.). Aquesta metodologia redueix la incertesa en l'estimació de recursos i proporciona una eina reproducible per a futures avaluacions geotèrmiques.

PARAULES CLAU: Geotèrmica, Petrofísica, Modelització 3D, Calor en el lloc, Calor recuperable.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's global scenario, marked by rising energy costs and the urgent need to abandon fossil fuels and shift to much cleaner alternative energies, geothermal energy has become one of the most promising renewable energy sources to achieve a sustainable energy transition. This energy, derived from the Earth's internal heat, has the capacity of offering a continuous and efficient energy supply, promoting more resilient, autonomous, and environmentally friendly energy systems. Its versatility allows applications both in the energy industry, such as underground heat storage, and even for electricity generation for social projects across entire regions.

Despite its advantages, geothermal energy still has limited implementation in the Spanish energy industry, mainly due to the limited knowledge of the resource and the high initial investment required for developing projects, especially due to the costs associated with drilling. This situation highlights the importance of reducing uncertainty and costs in the exploratory stages through geological, geophysical, and petrophysical studies that allow accurate modeling of temperature distribution at depth, identification of thermal anomalies, and quantification of the available energy resource. Aquifers are fundamental because they store and transport geothermal heat, provide the hydraulic connectivity needed for fluid circulation and define target reservoirs.

The Loranca sub-basin, located in the northeast of the Alto Guadiana region in central Spain, represents an area where the potential for geothermal energy development is still unknown. This area is characterized by the presence of a Jurassic unit composed mainly of massive limestones and dolostones, which constitute the main carbonate aquifer of the region (del Pozo Tejado et al., 2019; JCCM, 2016). It is a scarcely studied area from a geothermal perspective, making it an ideal candidate for research evaluating this renewable resource.

This work proposes a methodology for estimating the geothermal potential of the Jurassic aquifer of the Loranca sub-basin (JCCM, 2016). The first step is the analysis of the petrophysical properties of 40 rock samples obtained and characterized in the laboratory. The second step is, using a previously developed 3D geological model as a base (Ayala et al., 2019) and the petrophysical properties measured in the laboratory, obtaining a one-dimensional thermal model to estimate the temperature distribution at depth. Finally, using a probabilistic volumetric method based on Monte Carlo simulations and the 3DHIP-Calculator Software (Piris et al., 2022), the Heat in Place (HIP) and the Recoverable Heat (Hrec) were evaluated, with the aim of quantifying the accumulated energy and the potentially recoverable energy per km² in the Jurassic aquifer.

This methodological approach not only allows reducing the uncertainty associated with geothermal energy exploration in the region, but also provides a solid technical basis for decision-making in future energy utilization initiatives. Likewise, the results obtained open the door to direct applications of geothermal energy, such as climate control, balneotherapy, or use in greenhouses, thus contributing to Spain's energy transition.

Likewise, this study is aligned with the objectives of the CSIC's COCREA project, which seeks to promote the transfer of scientific knowledge to society and industry through collaborative open-innovation projects, thereby contributing to the development and practical application of geothermal energy in Spain.

2. OBJECTIVES

The overarching aim of this MSc thesis is to assess the geothermal potential of the Jurassic aquifer of the Loranca sub-basin area (NE of Alto Guadiana region, central Spain) with the heat in place method, based on the integration of a geological model and the development of a 3D thermal model, and experimentally obtained thermal petrophysical parameters and density from rock samples.

The specific objectives are:

1. To determine the thermal petrophysical properties (thermal conductivity, thermal effusivity, thermal diffusivity and specific heat capacity) and density of the main outcropping geological units through the laboratory analysis of rock samples obtained in the field.
2. To generate 3D thermal models of the study area using Geomodeller software, based on a previous geological model (Ayala et al., 2019) and integrating the thermal petrophysical data obtained in the laboratory simulating a temperature distribution model per unit.
3. To evaluate the geothermal potential of the target unit (Jurassic) by calculating the Heat in Place (HIP) and the Recoverable Heat (Hrec) using the 3DHIP-Calculator software, through a probabilistic approach based on Monte Carlo simulations.
4. To analyze and identify areas with the highest feasibility for geothermal exploitation of the Jurassic aquifer based on the results obtained, considering recovery, efficiency, load, and service life factors of systems utilizing low-enthalpy geothermal resources.

3. GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The Loranca sub-basin is part of the Alto Guadiana area (Central Spain) (*Figure 1*), which in turn is belongs to the eastern sector of the main Tagus Basin. Loranca sub-basin is separated from the Madrid sub-basin by the Sierra de Altomira (Díaz-Molina et al., 1995; Civis & Vera., 2004). The Tagus Basin is a Cenozoic intraplate basin bounded by the Spanish Central System to the northwest, the Iberian Range to the northeast, and the Toledo Mountains to the southwest (Ayala et al., 2019 and references therein).

The study area has an extent of 1,200 km², developed as a piggyback-type basin during the Late Oligocene to Early Miocene (Díaz-Molina et al., 1995). This refers to a basin formed atop a tectonically active thrust sheet. The sub-basin exhibits folds related to west-verging, N–S-trending thrusts (Ayala et al., 2019). It is important to highlight that a detachment occurs along a regional horizon mainly composed of evaporites and clays belonging to the Middle–Upper Triassic Keuper (Gómez et al.,

1996; Muñoz-Martín & De Vicente, 1998). Previous studies describe the tectonic context as the result of Alpine compression acting upon older Triassic extensional structures, generating a belt of low-thickness folds and thrusts (Muñoz-Martín & De Vicente, 1998).

Figure 1: Geological map of the study area modified at 1:50 000 scale (IGME, 2019) and (Rincon et al., 2023) 1) SectionMedio_2 (Figure 10A) and 2) Section ddprima (Figure 10B). Ng_q - Neogene-Quaternary; pg - Paleogene; cr_sup - Upper Cretaceous; cr_inf- Lower Cretaceous; ju - Jurassic

The study area presents significant deformation structures, notably the Zafra de Záncara (El Hito) and Rambla anticlines. These folds originated as a result of compressive stresses transmitted into the interior of the Iberian Plate, as noted by Civis & Vera (2004), affecting rocks ranging from the Triassic–Cretaceous to the Cenozoic (Querol, 1989). The size of these anticlines varies between 5 and 20 km, with the Zafra de Záncara anticline being the most prominent (Ayala et al., 2019). These structures are oriented NNW–SSE and present a marked asymmetric character defined by the different dip of their limbs. According to historical seismic data and gravimetric-inversion modelling, deformation processes beneath the sedimentary cover initiated in the Triassic, associated with extensional stresses that generated normal faults and grabens. Such structures were later inverted during compressive phases, thus configuring the current geological architecture (Guimerà & Álvaro, 1990; IGME, 2009; Valcárcel-Rodríguez, M. 2015; Ayala et al., 2019).

In terms of the stratigraphy, the study area includes various geological formations, especially Jurassic, the aquifer-bearing units and hence are key for geothermal exploration. The generalized stratigraphic column of the area includes ages from the Paleozoic to the Neogene–Quaternary, as described in previous works by Díaz-Molina et al. (1995), Gómez et al. (1996), Muñoz-Martín & De Vicente (1998), and Ayala et al. (2019).

- **Paleozoic Basement:** It is mainly composed by slates, Armorican quartzite and granite at a depth of $-1,195$ to $-3,500$ m.
- **Lower Triassic:** It is composed of buntsandstein sandstones and Muschelkalk limestones. The thickness varies between 200 and 400 m (Ayala et al., 2019) and depth between $-1,044$ and $-2,400$ m approximately.
- **Upper Triassic Keuper:** It mainly consists of evaporites (gypsum), shales, clastic sandstones, and carbonatic limestones. The depth varies from $-2,189$ m to $+40$ m, and the thickness ranges from tens of metres to over 1,000 m.
- **Middle–Upper Jurassic:** It is mainly formed by platform limestones, dolostones with chert, and interbedded fractured marls. This formation is of greatest interest to the project because it forms the target aquifer. Its depth varies from $+944$ to $-1,525$ m, and the thickness is approximately 1,000 m.

Finally, at the hydrogeological context, the Jurassic unit is formed, from base to top, by massive limestones and dolomites of the Lias-Dogger and especially of the Upper Jurassic, very karstifiable rocks that form the main carbonate aquifer of the water body (Del Pozo Tejado et al., 2019; JCCM, 2016).

- **Cretaceous:** These are shallow-marine limestones and dolostones, with a depth ranging from -652 to $+974$ m, and a thickness of 250–500 m.
- **Paleogene:** It is composed of shales, siltstones, and sandstones, with a depth between $+70$ and $-1,005$ m.
- **Neogene–Quaternary:** They are continental siliciclastic deposits (mudstones, sandstones, marly limestones, and conglomerates), with a depth from $+1,035$ to $+462$ m, and a thickness from a few tens to over 500 m depending on the area.

The petrophysical properties were determined using laboratory rock-sample data from outcrops, data from the El Hito-1 well, and regional petrophysical databases from IGME (Pueyo et al., 2015; IGME, 2019).

4. METHODOLOGY

The preliminary phase of the project involved compiling geological data and reviewing all relevant literature for the study area, and the methodology followed can be divided specifically into three parts: (1) measurement of petrophysical data from rock samples of Alto Guadiana Basin area in the laboratory (density and thermal properties); (2) calculation of the temperature distribution model in a 3D geological model with the software Geomodeller; and (3) the determination of heat in place and recoverable heat by means of Montecarlo simulations based on the geological and thermal models

using 3DHIP-Calculator software, which will allow assessing the geothermal potential of the area of interest.

4.1. Determination of rock density and thermal properties of rock samples

For the thermal property characterization of the samples, a total of 40 rock samples were analyzed, representing the main outcropping lithological units identified in the Alto Guadiana area, that are similar to the ones outcropping in the study area (*Table 2*). However, there are no samples for some ages, such as the Cretaceous and Paleogene, so it was necessary to take the data from the literature.

The measured thermal properties were the thermal conductivity (λ) and thermal effusivity (e), fundamental parameters to be used in geothermal modelling. The measurements were made using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) method with the C-Therm thermal instrument (*Figure 2*) under stable ambient temperature and atmospheric pressure conditions. C-Therm is a portable device widely employed in geological and geothermal studies (Harris et al., 2014). This method employs a one-sided heat sensor that increases its temperature by approximately 1°C due to an electrical current pulse, while recording the voltage change at the source/sensor (Labus & Labus, 2018).

Figure 2: 1) C-therm thermal sensor 1A) sensor with rock sample 2) C-therm instrument for calculating the petrophysical properties of rocks. 3) Laboratory work at the University of Barcelona.

Accordingly, the instrument required prior calibration with a ceramic or polymer material, serving as a conductive base and contact agent between the sensor and the polished sample. Distilled water was used as a contact agent to reduce the thermal resistance and error (Harris et al., 2014; Labus & Labus, 2018). Following the instructions of the manual, each reading must achieve a maximum error of 1.2% (RSD); if exceeded, the measurement is deemed incorrect and unreliable and must be repeated.

Figure 3: 1) Diamond saw cutting of rock samples used in the laboratory. 2) Sample AG_M1 (Lacustrine Limestones core – Neogene).

The 40 samples were prepared beforehand by flat-cutting and surface cleaning (Figure 3), ensuring optimal contact with the instrument's sensor—indispensable for correct readings (A contact agent was used between the sensor and the sample, which was distilled water, which helps improve heat transfer during measurement), as a rough or particulate surface would yield erroneous RSD values and fail validation. Measurements were conducted in the laboratory of the University of Barcelona's Faculty of Earth Sciences. Our environmental conditions, which do not exceed 22-25 °C, complying with the protocol and recommendations of the instrument. Five measurements were taken for each point chosen on the sample surface to ensure the accuracy of the results, calculating the average of the values in the collection and processing of the data. For each sample, two or three measures were taken on each flat cut surface (Figure 4). The number of measures depended on the size of the surface where the data were taken, also whether the sample had small variations of interest on its surface. All information generated from the various readings were stored within the instrument's proprietary TRIDENT software.

After the laboratory measurements, the raw data from each measurement were processed and compiled, then exported as .csv spreadsheets generated by TRIDENT software for statistical analysis. For each sample, the final mean values of thermal conductivity and thermal effusivity were calculated, discarding readings with errors, discrepancies, or outliers exhibiting high coefficients of variation (RSD) exceeding 1.2% (C-Therm, 2021).

Values exceeding 1.2% RSD are considered erroneous. These outliers in the results of the software, were commonly attributable to rock porosity, fractures, or jointing at the sensor contact with the rock or alteration; the presence of voids allowed the contact agent (distilled water) to be absorbed by the sample, making accurate, consistent readings more difficult in highly porous specimens. For example, quartzites and gypsums samples were excluded from the process due to their high error rates, high porosity, high fracturing and unreliable petrophysical results. Alternative methods—beyond the scope of this work—would be required to determine the petrophysical properties of those samples.

Ultimately, it was processed and standardized the dataset and ensured consistency in accordance with the lithological properties observed for each unit.

Figure 4: 1) Rock sample referenced as AG_32 (Alto Guadiana sample 32), with lithology consisting of slate, greywacke, and calcschist, and belonging to the Precambrian geological unit. Process of measuring its thermal petrophysical properties, with the C-THERM sensor at the bottom and a weight at the top to prevent the sample from moving during data collection. 2) Measurement point and 3) 40 rock samples of different lithologies analyzed in the laboratory of different lithologies.

Thermal conductivity is the principal parameter for defining heat transfer by conduction in rock media; thus, this property allows estimation of temperature distribution at given depth for each unit in the geological model (Clauser & Huenges, 1995; Fuchs & Förster, 2014). Thermal conductivity is a key parameter that relates the surface heat flow with the geothermal gradient. Surface heat flow (mW/m^2) is expressed by the equation:

$$q = -\lambda * \frac{dT}{dz}$$

where q is the surface heat flow, λ is the thermal conductivity and dT/dz is the geothermal gradient, which varies depending on the region. For this study, although the average value is $35^\circ\text{C}/\text{km}$ for the central part of the Iberian Peninsula, measures in different piezometres in the Alto Guadiana Basin indicate a range between $15^\circ\text{C}/\text{km}$ and $35^\circ\text{C}/\text{km}$, so we have used three different geothermal gradients in our work. The relationship with thermal conductivity (λ) is fundamental for estimating temperatures at depth and evaluating geothermal resources. Thermal effusivity, by contrast, is the capacity of a rock to exchange heat with its surroundings and is very useful for interpreting and analysing transient thermal conduction processes (Popov et al., 1999).

The density of each sample was determined experimentally via Archimedes' principle (Figure 5). Each dry sample was fully submerged in a vessel of water, and the displaced volume was measured by the change in water mass before and after immersion (Falco, Franceschelli, & Maro., 2001). From this

information, the volume of each sample was obtained and, by relating it to its completely dry mass, the density was calculated using the formula:

$$\rho = \frac{M_{\text{dry}}}{V_{\text{displaced}}} * \rho_f$$

Figure 5: Calculation of densities of the 40 rock samples using Archimedes' principle method.

Where M_{dry} is the mass of the rock, $V_{\text{displaced}}$ is the volume of displaced water, and ρ_f is the density of the fluid (Lin et al., 2015), which for water is taken as a reference of 1000 kg/m³.

However, since there were no samples of Cretaceous and Paleogene ages, the densities provided by Ayala et al., 2019 had to be used, which in turn came from two sources: data from the El Hito-1 borehole (Lanaja & Navarro, 1987) and previous petrophysical compilations (Pueyo et al., 2015). The data were compiled in the following (Table 3).

The specific heat capacity (C_p) was calculated for each sample. This parameter was not measured directly by the C-Therm device but was estimated from the obtained values of thermal conductivity (k), thermal effusivity (e), and density (ρ) using the following relationship (Harris et al., 2014).

$$C_p = \frac{e^2}{k * \rho}$$

The specific heat capacity (C_p) was incorporated to complete and enhance the robustness of the calculated thermal petrophysical properties. C_p indicates the amount of thermal energy that a unit mass of rock can store per degree of temperature change (Clauser & Huenges, 1995), and varies according to lithology and temperature, especially in carbonates (Merriman et al., 2018).

The mean value for each petrophysical property—thermal conductivity, thermal effusivity, and specific heat capacity—was calculated per lithological unit, thus providing a consistent set of thermal parameters for integration into the geothermal model of the study area in Geomodeller. The petrophysical values of the lithologies that are in the software such as Cretaceous and Paleogene and that have not been measured in the laboratory, due to lack of samples, have been obtained from the literature (Pueyo et al., 2015) and from the UNE ISO 100715-1:2014 (AENOR, 2014) standard.

4.2 Thermal Modelling 3D in Geomodeller Software

4.2.1 3D Geological Model

The three-dimensional geological model used for this work comes from the work by Ayala et al. (2019). The model has an extension of 20 km × 25 km, with a depth of –3.5 km. The top of the model is a digital elevation model with a 100 m mesh. This geological model was carried out using Geomodeller software from Intrepid Geophysics. Details of the modelling process can be found in Ayala et al., (2019)

Geologically, the model depicts the area of the Zafra de Záncara and La Rambla anticlines (*Figure 6*), which are located, as previously mentioned, in the Loranca sub-basin within the Tagus Basin. The model was built from twelve geological cross-sections that were based on the reinterpretation of vintage seismic lines in the area. The surface geological data comes from the MAGNA 1:50,000 Geological Map of the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain (IGME). The geological model was refined through inversion of gravimetry data (Ayala et al., 2019).

Figure 6: 3D geological model, Altomira mountain range area, modeling of the La Rambla and Zafra de Záncara anticlines, modified from (Ayala et al., 2019).

The units of the model are: (1) Paleozoic basement, (2) Triassic Buntsandstein–Muschelkalk, (3) Triassic Keuper, (4) Jurassic, (5) Lower–Middle and Upper Cretaceous, (6) Paleogene, and (7) Neogene-Quaternary. According to the stratigraphic column (*Figure 7*), the Jurassic rocks are predominantly carbonate in nature, composed mainly of limestones and dolomites. According to several authors (Rincón et al., 2025), geological studies conducted in the area indicate that the main hydrogeological unit is located within the Jurassic rocks. This is due to the presence of fractures and dissolution processes (secondary porosity) in the rocks, which allow for high permeability values, facilitating groundwater storage. At the base of the Jurassic stratigraphic unit lies the Keuper Formation, which acts as a cap rock, primarily composed of clays and evaporites deposited during the Upper Triassic.

Figure 7: Stratigraphic column of the study area (stratigraphic column created using Sedlog software).

To build the thermal model in Geomodeller software is a process that follows a sequence of indispensable steps with the objective of calculating the temperature field as a function of the geological geometry, taking into account the thermal properties of the different lithologies and boundary conditions (Intrepid Geophysics & BRGM, 2014; Calcagno et al., 2008a; Guillén et al., 2008b).

4.2.2 Assignment of Thermal Properties

Mean values of thermal conductivity ($W/m \cdot K$), radiogenic heat production (W/m^3) and density were assigned to each of the geological units of the model. The radiogenic heat production corresponds to the heat generated by the radioactive decay of elements such as uranium, thorium and potassium. Since we do not have values of K, Th and U for the different lithologies. For the radiogenic heat production parameter (W/m^3), a constant value of $1 \times 10^{-6} W/m^3$ (i.e., 0.000001 watts per cubic meter) was adopted. The value remained uniform throughout the modeled volume, as the thermal model focuses primarily on the Jurassic carbonate unit, which has a relatively homogeneous lithology dominated by platform limestones and dolomites. Similarly, the remaining geological units have comparable lithologies with minimal compositional variability. This representative value was selected within the typical ranges reported in the literature for sedimentary rocks (e.g., Vilà et al., 2010).

This assumption is supported by Fernández et al. (1998), who observed that the contribution of internal heat production can be insignificant in certain areas of the Tertiary basins, especially those characterized by very low enthalpy.

4.2.3 Boundary Conditions

Once the petrophysical data had been assigned for each unit, the calculation of the temperature distribution was carried out. The module separates the geological model into a voxel mesh of $80 \times 80 \times 151$ cells, with a cell size of $250 \times 312 \times 30.13$ meters. The number and, therefore, size of cells were chosen in order not to overload the system due to hardware limitations. Next, the software solves the steady-state heat conduction equation using an iterative Gauss–Seidel finite-difference scheme, which is a numerical technique for solving systems of linear equations (Cortés Rosas et al., 2019). For this, two boundary conditions must be defined.

- **Surface Temperature:** A constant value of $14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was fixed at the topographic surface of the model. This value was selected as a representative estimate of the regional annual average ground temperature corrected for the subsurface in the study area Alto Guadiana, central Spain (AEMET, 2025)
- **Surface Heat Flow:** A value of 70 mW/m^2 was chosen for the model surface heat flow, a value obtained from the study by Fernández et al. (1998), which analyzes the thermal regime of the Iberian Peninsula. This value is coherent with heat fluxes measured in the central-southern region of the Iberian Peninsula.

4.2.4 Computing geothermal solutions

Once assigned the thermal properties and established the boundary conditions, we have run the calculations with a maximum of 100000 iterations and a maximum thermal residual value of $0.0001\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. If the largest change in temperature between two iterations is smaller than this value, GeoModeller assumes the model has reached a stable solution and stops the iterations).

Once the iterations were completed and the model generated, it will be stored and ready to explore the results using GeoModeller's "Grids and Meshes" visualization tools. The result is a 3D field of temperature distribution in depth that allows analysis of potentially anomalous zones (*Figure 8*) and (*Figure 9*).

4.3 Geothermal Assessment Using 3DHIP-Calculator Software

The third step of this work consisted of calculating the geothermal potential through an evaluation of the geothermal resource in our area of interest. For this purpose, the 3D-HIP-Calculator software was used (Piris et al., 2022). This software employs the volumetric heat in place method defined by the USGS (Muffler & Cataldi, 1978), combined with Monte Carlo simulations.

The estimation of the geothermal resource by volumetric methods is based on the use of known temperature values, such as thermal conductivity, radiogenic heat production, surface temperature and surface heat flow. These thermal parameters are essential for the calculation of the 3D model of temperatures at depth, which in turn will be used in its entirety for the calculation of the so-called Heat in Place (HIP). And from this value, and applying a recovery factor, the recoverable heat is obtained (Torre Ruiz, 2022).

This method is suitable for the evaluation of reservoirs in deep sedimentary basins, as it is based on available information from the area, such as the stratigraphic column and the petrophysical parameters of the geological units requirements that this work methodology meets. The Heat in Place (HIP) method combines the volumetric approach with Monte Carlo simulations in order to obtain an approximate estimate of a geothermal reservoir's potential. Monte Carlo simulations are a probabilistic mathematical simulation method, widely used in studies with a high degree of uncertainty and unpredictability. Unlike a standard forecasting model, simulations predict a set of outcomes based on an estimated range of values rather than a deterministic or fixed input value (Piris et al., 2022).

Since the 3DHIP-Calculator software is programmed in MATLAB, it probabilistically evaluates each voxel of each geological and thermal model entered, taking into account the input data and generating geothermal potential results corresponding to the area we want to assess. In this work, the geothermal potential of the lower aquifer in the Sierra de Altomira area, belonging to the Jurassic, was specifically evaluated.

Muffler and Cataldi (1978) proposed the following equations for calculating Heat in Place (HIP) and Recoverable Heat (Hrec). HIP which allows estimating the geothermal resource and the recoverable fraction of a subsurface reservoir (Piris et al., 2022).

$$HIP = V \cdot [(\Phi \cdot \rho_F \cdot CF) + ((1 - \Phi) \cdot \rho_R \cdot CR)] \cdot (T_r - T_i)$$

where HIP is the stored energy (kJ), V is the volume of the cube voxel of the 3D geological model (m^3), Φ is the porosity (by unit), ρ_F and ρ_R are the fluid density and rock density in (kg/m^3), respectively, CF and CR are the specific heat capacity of fluid (F) and rock (R) ($kJ/kg \cdot ^\circ C$), respectively, T_r is the reservoir temperature in the 3D model ($^\circ C$) and T_i is the reinjection temperature, which is taken as a reference ($^\circ C$).

Once the HIP value has been obtained, the recoverable heat value (Hrec) is calculated using the following formula, which takes into account the thermal power that can be produced during the useful life of a given plant or project (Piris et al., 2022).

$$H_{rec} = \frac{HIP \cdot C_e \cdot R}{T_{live} \cdot L_f}$$

where H_{rec} is the recoverable heat (kW), C_e is the efficiency factor, R is the recovery factor (default 0.20), T_{live} is the plant lifetime (s) and L_f is the Plant factor.

The recovery factor (R) depends on the porosity and permeability of the rock, as well as on the system design, the depth of the wells, and the thermal and hydraulic conditions (Torre Ruiz, 2022). In preliminary assessments, where these data are often uncertain, estimated values are used. For example, an accepted range goes from 0 (when there is no recoverable fluid) up to 0.20, with 0.10 being the default value used by the 3DHIP-Calculator software. For this case, we used 0.20 as the best-case scenario.

Regarding the remaining parameters, Pastor et al. (2010) proposes the following reference values: For the efficiency factor (C_e) 0.1 is considered a common value for low-enthalpy geothermal plants. For the load factor (LD) 0.75 is an average value associated with plant design. For the reinjection of temperature of 15 °C. And the plant's lifespan is estimated at approximately 25 years. All these values were kept as default due to the scarcity of available data (Table 1).

To carry out the evaluation of the geothermal potential of the Jurassic unit in the study area, both the geological model and the thermal model were imported into the 3DHIP-Calculator software. These models were exported from Geomodeller in CSV format. The preliminary results of piezometer studies currently being carried out by IGME-CSIC in the Upper Guadiana area show that the geothermal gradient in the area has a range between 15 and 35°C/km. Because of that data, we have carried out the calculations HIP and Hrec of the Jurassic aquifer using three geothermal gradient values of 15, 25 and 35 °C/km (Rincón et al., 2025).

For the geothermal evaluation, the input data were introduced only for the geological level under study (Jurassic, that corresponds to lithology n.4 in the model).

Table 1: The values used in the table correspond to the parameters needed to calculate Recoverable Heat (Hrec) and Heat in Place (HIP). Due to a lack of data, the default values from the software, as previously stated, have been used. The selected Target n.4 corresponds to Jurassic.

Parameters for geothermal potential estimation	Value
Thermal Gradient °C/km	15, 25, 35
Surface Temperature °C	14
Number of Simulations	1000
Target unit	Jurassic
Select Target	4
Upper Depth (m.a.s.l.)	-50
Lower Depth (m.a.s.l.)	-1520
Porosity	0.230
Fluid density (kg/m3)	1020
Fluid specific heat capacity (kJ/kg °C)	4.8
Rock specific heat capacity (kJ/kg °C)	0.72
Recovery Factor	0.20

5. RESULTS

5.1. PETROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF ROCK SAMPLES

The laboratory characterization of 40 rock samples from the study area allowed the identification of key variables associated with each lithology. According to *Table 3*, certain lithologies such as those of granite, gypsum, sandstone, quartzite, and marly limestone, showed thermal conductivity and effusivity results classified as Failed. This classification is due to the relative standard deviation (%RSD) exceeding the limit allowed by the manufacturer (1.2%) for both parameters (C-Therm, 2021), thus rendering these results invalid.

This error is mainly attributed to the high porosity and alteration of the sandstone and quartzite, the high fracturing of the gypsums and the granite alteration. When distilled water was used as the contact agent between the rock and the sensor, it was observed that at the beginning of the measurement, the water was rapidly absorbed by the rock. This caused the loss of the contact agent on the surface, resulting in measurement errors from the instrument (five measurements were taken on each polished face of every sample).

To address this issue, it would have been advisable to implement alternative measurement techniques, such as the Flex Transient Plane Source (designed for porous materials), or to use a contact agent less prone to absorption. However, in order to maintain methodological consistency, the same contact agent was used for all samples. Examples of the results obtained are displayed in *Table 2*. The completed Table with all the samples analyzed is an Annex.

Table 2: Laboratory results of petrophysical properties of part of the rock samples collected from the study area. See the full Table in appendix.

PETROPHYSICAL DATA COMPILED FROM LABORATORY SAMPLES								
DESCRIPTION				FINAL DATA PETROPHYSICAL THERMAL PROPERTIES				
SAMPLE	LITHOLOGY	AGE	MODEL UNIT	Thermal Conductivity λ (W/mK)	Thermal effusivity e [(W·s ^{1/2})/(m ² ·K)]	Density (kg/m ³)	Thermal diffusivity [m ² /s]	Specific heat capacity C_p [J/(K·g·K)]
CALIBRATION								
AG_M1	Lacustrine Limestones - Core	Upper Miocene Aquifer	Neogeno - Quaternary	3.34	2595.00	2675	1.65E-06	754.82
AG_M2	Lacustrine Limestones - Core	Upper Miocene Aquifer	Neogeno - Quaternary	2.91	2382.68	2690	1.49E-06	726.01
AG_M3	dolomites with carnellians	Lower Jurassic Aquifer	Jurassic	2.74	2297.57	2750	1.42E-06	701.33
CALIBRATION								
AG_17	Guindo Slates	Middle Ordovician	Paleozoic	4.43	3115.92	2603	2.02E-06	841.50
AG_19	Slate and quartzite Quarry	Upper Ordovician	Paleozoic	5.99	3804.52	2627	2.48E-06	919.84
AG_12	Granite	Carboniferous	Paleozoic	2.33	2089.63	2540	1.24E-06	737.86
AG_33	Granite	Carboniferous	Paleozoic	2.83	2344.90	2718	1.46E-06	714.69
AG_2	Quartzites; "Pochico" Layers	Lower Ordovician	Paleozoic	3.09	2473.30	2828	1.56E-06	699.67
AG_21	Slate and quartzite	Upper Ordovician	Paleozoic	4.84	3302.81	2599	2.15E-06	866.76
AG_11	marl limestones	Pliocene	Neogeno - Quaternary	2.39	2118.10	2507	1.27E-06	750.28
AG_3	Cuarcita Armoricana	Lower Ordovician	Paleozoic	5.69	3676.90	2751	2.40E-06	863.49
AG_1	Slates; Layers with <i>Tristani</i>	Middle Ordovician	Paleozoic	3.89	2861.87	2777	1.85E-06	758.36
CALIBRATION								
AG_30	Calcareous schists, Slates and Greywackes	Precambrian, Vendian	Precambrian	3.63	2737.48	2675	1.76E-06	771.61

For each unit of the geological model, the following results shown the ranges of thermal conductivity, a parameter that was subsequently averaged for use in the model calculations:

1. **Neogene–Quaternary:** Rocks with lithologies such as lacustrine limestones (core), marly limestones, and basalts showed thermal conductivity (λ) values of 2.91–3.34, 2.39, and 2.16 W/m·K, respectively. The average value adopted for the thermal model was 2.75 W/m·K.
2. **Paleogene–Cretaceous:** It was not possible to directly calculate thermal parameters due to the lack of representative samples. Instead, thermal conductivity (λ) values were adopted from UNE-EN ISO 100715-1:2014 (AENOR, 2014), based on the lithologies of the unit described by Ayala et al. (2019), with averages of 2.40 and 2.82 W/m·K, respectively.
3. **Jurassic:** Hydrogeologically relevant unit. Dolomitic limestones and dolostones exhibited thermal conductivity (λ) values between 2.72–3.54 and 2.45–2.74 W/m·K, respectively, with an overall average of 2.94 W/m·K.
4. **Triassic:** Gypsum and carbonates, The only value measured in the laboratory was 3.33. As there was only one sample, the value for the thermal model was taken from UNE-EN ISO 100715-1:2014 (AENOR,2014), which is 2.3 W/m·K.
5. **Paleozoic:** Rocks with diverse lithologies (slates, granites, quartzites, among others) presented an average thermal conductivity (λ) of 4.44 W/m·K.
6. **Precambrian:** Various lithologies, including slates, greywackes, gypsums, calc-schists, and carbonates, showed thermal conductivity (λ) values ranging from 3.34–4.10 W/m·K. The average value was 3,72 W/m·K was not taken into account in the model, as it is not found in the stratigraphic column.

The thermal diffusivity values were averaged using the same procedure applied for thermal conductivity (λ). Based on these values and the density data obtained in the laboratory using Archimedes' principle, the specific heat capacity (C_p) was calculated following the methodology previously described. These values are compiled in *Table 2*.

The values of densities obtained from the Archimedes' principle were compiled and organized in the following *Table 3*.

Table 3: Densities calculated in the laboratory using Archimedes' principle and correlation of geological units of samples vs. units of the geological model described on Ayala et al. (2019). The complete table is in appendix.

SAMPLE DENSITIES - ARCHIMEDES' PRINCIPLE								
SAMPLE ID	TYPE	AGE	AGES MODEL LR-EH	Ma (g)	Mw (g)	MODEL DENSITIES (g/cm ³)	SAMPLE DENSITIES (g/cm ³)	SAMPLE DENSITIES (kg/m ³)
AG 1	Slates: Layers with Tristani	Middle Ordovician	Paleozoic	321	205,4	2,75	2,78	2777
AG 2	Quartzites; "Pochico" layers	Lower Ordovician	Paleozoic	102,1	66	2,75	2,83	2828
AG 3	Armorican quartzite	Lower Ordovician	Paleozoic	82,8	52,7	2,75	2,75	2751
AG 4	Marl limestone	Miocene	Neogeno - Quaternary	66,4	35,4	2,28 - 2,38	2,14	2142
AG 5	Dolomites	Jurassic	Jurassic	134,1	85,1	2,65	2,74	2737
AG 6	Sandstones	Triassic	Triassic	197,6	107,5	2,50 - 2,56	2,19	2193
AG 7	Gypsum	Triassic	Triassic	81,2	46,1	2,50 - 2,56	2,31	2313
AG 8	Dolomites	Jurassic	Jurassic	175,7	111,9	2,65	2,75	2754
AG 9	Armorican quartzite	Lower Ordovician	Paleozoic	149,9	95	2,75	2,73	2730
AG 10	Dolomites	Jurassic	Jurassic	126,6	80,2	2,65	2,73	2728
AG 11	Marl limestones	Pliocene	Neogeno - Quaternary	89	53,5	2,28 - 2,38	2,51	2507
AG 12	Granite	Carbonifero	Paleozoic	119,9	72,7	2,75	2,54	2540
AG 13	Carbonates	Triassic	Triassic	276,1	177,8	2,50 - 2,56	2,81	2809
AG 14	Dolomites	Jurassic	Jurassic	241,4	150,1	2,65	2,64	2644
AG 15	Granite	Carboniferous	Paleozoic	180,1	109,3	2,75	2,54	2544

5.2. TEMPERATURE THERMAL MODEL – GEOMODELLER SOFTWARE

The properties thermal conductivity (λ) and density were assigned for each unit from experimental values obtained in the laboratory. As we did not have samples of the Cretaceous and Paleogene units, which are essential for calculating the petrophysical parameters of those ages, it was necessary to take these values from bibliographic sources (UNE-EN ISO 100715-1:2014).

Figure 8.1 and *Figure 8.2* show the three-dimensional volumes of the thermal model with vertical cross sections representing the temperature distribution to depths of approximately -3500 m. A progressive increase in temperature with depth is observed, from $\sim 14^\circ\text{C}$ at surface to approximately $50\text{--}55^\circ\text{C}$ in the deepest areas, assuming a surface heat flow of around 70 mW/m^2 . Considering higher surface heat flow would result in elevated temperatures. Similarly, *Figure 8.2* shows a slight temperature variation between the yellow and red zones, which corresponds specifically to the axial axis of the La Zafra anticline (*Figure 9*).

In this case, the temperature distribution is observed to be quite uniform across the units. This is attributed to their similar thermal conductivity values.

Figure 9 presents a perspective view of the complete model, integrating the surface geological map with vertical temperature distributions. The thermal model integrates both structural and thermal data

Figure 8: 8.1 and 8.2) 3D depth temperature model. A gradual transition of the thermal gradient can be observed from surface temperatures ($\sim 14^\circ\text{C}$) to maximum values of $50\text{--}55^\circ\text{C}$ at depths close to 3500 m.

The *Figure 10* corresponds to structural cross-sections of the geological model used, representing both the geological units of the area and the modelled temperature distribution at depth. In sectors dominated by Jurassic and Triassic units, intermediate temperatures ($40\text{--}50^\circ\text{C}$) are observed at depths of $1500\text{--}2500$ m, indicating potential interest for direct-use low-enthalpy geothermal applications. Additionally, the folded and faulted structures observed in the model locally influence the thermal distribution, generating slight perturbations in the regional thermal gradient.

Figure 9: Perspective view of the final vertical temperature model, with the map of the study area at the top. The legend is temperature, blue for coldest, red for hottest.

Figure 10: Depth temperature model shown by two vertical sections of the 3D thermal model. The colors represent the temperature (in °C), from low values in blue to high values in red, according to the scale shown. The lines delimit the different geological units of the subsoil, allowing us to observe how the temperature varies depending on the geometry and arrangement of these units. Sections: A) SectionMedio_2 and B) Section ddprima.

5.3. HEAT IN PLACE AND RECOVERABLE HEAT

The input model is the export from Geomodeler with $80 \times 80 \times 151$ voxel blocks and a cell size of $250 \times 312 \times 30.13$ meters consisting of geological and thermal models in text-format (CSV). These exported files must be perfectly aligned in their voxel dimensions and values; otherwise, discrepancies may lead to errors in the software and incoherent results.

Using the export from the Geomodeler geological model, the 3DHIP-Calculator software was used to exclusively analyze the carbonate aquifer of the Jurassic unit. The depth range defined for this analysis was between -50 and -1520 m, based on the depth of the unit in the study area.

Three simulations were performed using geothermal gradients of 15, 25, and 35 °C/km, generating temperature distribution curves with depth (*Figure 11*). This increase is expected, as temperatures rise proportionally with the geothermal gradient. However, even in the highest gradient scenario (35 °C/km), the maximum temperature reached is 100 °C. This indicates that the geothermal potential of the Jurassic unit is low, making it suitable exclusively for direct-use geothermal applications.

Figure 11: Depth temperature distribution, represented in three thermal scenarios with geothermal gradients of 1) 15, 2) 25 and 3) 35 °C/km. The red lines indicate the study reservoir (Jurassic Aquifer). The progressive increase in temperature from the surface ($\sim 14^{\circ}\text{C}$) to depths of around -50 to -1520 m is shown. (Own, taken from 3DHIP-calculator).

Then, by introducing the parameters described in the methodology chapter, corresponding to the “Heat in Place” volumetric method, the following graphs are generated (*Figure 12*).

Figure 12: Histograms of stored energy values in the reservoir (HIP) in picojoules (PJ) for the three geothermal gradient scenarios (15, 25, and 35 °C/km) at a depth of -50 to -1520 m (Jurassic Unit). (3DHIPcalculator).

In the *Figure 13*, these three graphs show the probability distribution curve of accumulated energy in the 3D model between the specified depths (-50 to -1520 m), identifying for each one three verticals that correspond to the probability of 10% (low confidence in green), 50%, and 90% (high confidence in blue and red, respectively) of the estimate. (3DHIP-calculator).

Figure 13: Cumulative probability curve of Jurassic resources between -50 and -1520 m. 1) Gradient 15°C/km 2) Gradient 25°C/km and 3) Gradient 35°C/km.

The Figure 14, showing distribution maps of accumulated energy (in PJ) between depths of -50 to -1520 m with a 50% probability (P50). The values shown are calculated as the vertical sum of the values of the model cubes with identical X and Y coordinates, divided by the area of the cubes, in km², expressed in picojoules (PJ) / km² units. This graph is repeated for probabilities of 10% (low confidence, P10), 50% (medium confidence, P50), and 90% (high confidence, P90). However, the figures only show those corresponding to P50 for the three geothermal gradient scenarios, in order to consider more realistic values (3DHIP-calculator).

Figure 14: Heat in Place (HIP), P50 of Jurassic between -50 and -1520 m. It is important to note that the color scale should be different for each map. However, the software generates all maps using the same default color palette, so it is recommended to interpret each one based on the specific values of its corresponding scale. 1) Gradient 15°C/km 2) Gradient 25°C/km and 3) Gradient 35°C/km.

3DHIP-Calculator calculates the heat in place and recoverable heat based on the parameters entered into the software. It calculates the total heat in place (combining all the cells in a unit). The 3DHIP-Calculator then displays in the following maps all the heat stored in a given area underground, in this case for the Jurassic unit. In other words, how much thermal energy is available per square area at the selected unit (Jurassic in this case) kilometer of surface area (Figure 14).

Similarly, the software calculates Recoverable Heat using the methodology described above. Hrec is the portion of heat in the subsoil that can actually be recovered using current technology and reasonable efficiency, depending on the type of geothermal energy. In other words, it is the amount of energy that can be generated or used per km² (Figure 15). This figure showing distribution maps of Hrec in kW in the reservoir defined between -50 and -1520 m. The values shown are calculated as the vertical sum of the values of the model cubes with identical X and Y coordinates, divided by the area of the cubes, in km², expressed in PJ/km² units. The figure shows only the value corresponding to P50, which has been selected as the most realistic value (3DHIP-calculator).

Figure 15: Recoverable Heat (Hrec), P50 of Jurassic between -50 and -1520 m. It is important to note that the color scale should be different for each map. However, the software generates all maps using the same default color palette, so it is recommended to interpret each one based on the specific values of its corresponding scale. 1) Gradient 15°C/km 2) Gradient 25°C/km and 3) Gradient 35°C/km.

Figure 16: Map showing temperature distribution at the top of the Jurassic geothermal reservoir (-50 to -1520 m) (3DHIP calculator). For the gradient of 25 °C/km. Temperature range between 42 to 56 °C.

Then, I compiled a definitive summary of the results obtained using the 3D-HIP software on the geothermal potential of the Jurassic reservoir (Table 4).

Table 4: Final results of the probabilistic analysis of the geothermal potential of the Jurassic reservoir, obtained with 3DHIP-Calculator. The table shows, for each geothermal gradient scenario, the estimated temperature at the top and bottom of the reservoir, together with the values of stored energy (HIP, in PJ/km²) and recoverable energy (Hrec, in kW/km²). The P10, P50, and P90 percentiles of the cumulative energy distribution curve are included, as well as the minimum and maximum values of HIP and Hrec according to the simulations performed.

JURASSIC	DEPTH (m.a.s.l.)		Acumulative energy probability distribution curve (PJ)			Heat in Place - HIP (PJ/Km2)		Recovable Heat - Hrec (kW/km2)		
	Distribution of Temperature at Depth (°C)					P50		P50		
	TOP (-50 m)	BASE (-1520 m)	P10	P50	P90	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	
Geothermal Gradient (°C/km)	15	30	52	2,72E+05	2,66E+05	2,66E+05	20	200	0.5 × 10 ⁴	4 × 10 ⁴
	25	40	78	4,61E+05	4,52E+05	4,42E+05	50	300	1 × 10 ⁴	6 × 10 ⁴
	35	50	100	6,51E+05	6,37E+05	6,23E+05	50	450	1 × 10 ⁴	9 × 10 ⁴

Finally, with the temperature map generated for the intermediate geothermal gradient (25 °C/km) and P50 probability, an overlay was performed on a topographic map from the Spanish National Geographic Institute in order to identify which populated areas are closest to the zones with temperatures of interest (*Figure 17*). In (1), the Casalonga housing development stands out, located in an area with temperatures ranging between approximately 54 and 56 °C. This would allow for the implementation of direct-use geothermal projects, such as district heating networks for the entire development, representing an energy-efficient and economically sustainable option. Similarly, this type of application could be explored in other towns such as Palomares del Campo and Torrecilla del Ducado (2) and (3). However, in the case of Montalbo (4), which presents lower temperatures, the use of geothermal energy could be considered for heating and cooling systems through geothermal heat pumps, which would be more suitable given the local subsurface conditions.

Figure 17: Temperature map overlaid on the topographic map of Spain (IGN). 1) Casalonga Urbanization, (2) Palomares del Campo (3) Torrebuçeit and (4) Montalbo. Map using a gradient of 25 °C/km.

6. DISCUSSION

The geothermal evaluation of the Jurassic carbonate aquifer in the Sierra de Altomira region confirms its classification as a low-enthalpy resource. The 3D thermal modelling, supported by petrophysical parameters experimentally obtained from 40 rock samples, yielded a relatively homogeneous temperature distribution with values ranging between ~ 14 °C at the surface and up to ~ 65 °C at depths of 3.5 km. Under the most optimistic geothermal gradient (35 °C/km), maximum temperatures around 100 °C were reached at the base of the Jurassic unit. These values are below the thresholds typically required for electricity generation using conventional binary geothermal systems but are suitable for direct-use applications such as space heating, balneotherapy, greenhouse agriculture, or low-temperature industrial processes.

The spatial homogeneity of the thermal field is primarily driven by the low variability in thermal conductivity across the geological units and the absence of significant thermal anomalies or high heat-production formations. Furthermore, the limited structural complexity of the reservoir (aside from localized anticlines such as Zafra de Záncara) does not induce major thermal gradients or convective features.

Despite the relatively low thermal potential, the methodological workflow applied—based on the integration of laboratory-derived petrophysical properties into a 3D geological and thermal model, and the subsequent probabilistic evaluation of Heat in Place and Recoverable Heat via Monte Carlo simulations—represents a robust and reproducible approach for preliminary geothermal resource assessment. This methodological workflow allows for transparent parameterization, error tracking, and scenario-based interpretation, which can be replicated in other regions of Spain where subsurface data are scarce.

The estimation of geothermal resources using the 3DHIP-Calculator provides quantitative insights into the usable energy content of the Jurassic unit. While the calculated Hrec values (up to 6×10^4 kW/km²) are modest, they represent a realistic and actionable estimation for local-scale exploitation. In particular, this resource could be strategically combined with energy demand centres (e.g., small towns or agro-industrial facilities) in the Loranca Sub-basin region, helping to reduce dependency on fossil fuels and decarbonize heating needs.

This study contributes to the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)** by advancing the geological and thermal characterization of the Alto Guadiana region for geothermal energy use. The identification of low-enthalpy geothermal reservoirs and the construction of 3D thermal models using petrophysical data support SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action), by promoting renewable energy alternatives and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. Furthermore, the use of open-access tools and interdisciplinary data integration aligns with SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), fostering innovation in sustainable subsurface resource assessment.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates the feasibility of evaluating low-enthalpy geothermal resources in sedimentary basins through a combination of petrophysical analysis, 3D geological and thermal modelling, and probabilistic volumetric assessment. The main conclusions are as follows:

1. The petrophysical properties measured in the laboratory, including thermal conductivity, thermal effusivity, specific heat capacity, and density, proved essential for defining realistic boundary conditions and thermal behaviour in the subsurface.
2. The 3D thermal model built using Geomodeller represents the temperature distribution in the area, confirming the absence of high-enthalpy geothermal anomalies but supporting the presence of usable low-grade heat in the Jurassic aquifer.
3. The Jurassic unit of the Sierra de Altomira region presents favourable characteristics for low-temperature geothermal use, particularly due to its carbonate lithology, moderate porosity, and sufficient thickness (about 1,000 m in the present case).
4. The use of Monte Carlo simulations through the 3DHIP-Calculator allowed the quantification of geothermal potential under different gradient scenarios, estimating for the best-case scenario (a gradient of 35°C/km) Heat in Place values of up to 300 PJ/km² and Recoverable Heat of up to 6×10⁴ kW/km².
5. Based on the results of the heat in place and recoverable heat maps, hotter and colder areas are identified, with the hottest spots being particularly interesting for exploration.
6. Although not suitable for power generation, the geothermal resource is sufficient for direct use applications that can support local energy transition strategies. For example for many towns in the area such as Casalonga, Palomares del Campo, Torrebuçeit and Montalbo, could contact public offices like IDAE (idae.es) to look for financial help in order to help developing district heating networks or geothermal air conditioning by heat pumps.
7. The methodological framework developed in this study can serve as a reference for future geothermal assessments in other sedimentary basins across Spain, particularly in data-limited regions where exploratory drilling has not yet been conducted.
8. Future research should aim to integrate hydraulic parameters and dynamic simulations, as well as consider socio-economic and environmental criteria for the practical implementation of geothermal systems in the Alto Guadiana region.

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